

FLPP MEET DPP

Version 1

Description

Projekts atbilst aktuālajam muzeoloģijas fokusam, kas uzsver sociālo iesaisti kā būtisku muzeju uzdevumu un ko apliecina Starptautiskās Muzeju padomes iniciatīva mainīt jēdziena "muzejs" definīciju, iekļaujot tajā muzeju pienākumu strādāt ar kopienu līdzdalību. Iedvesmojoties no muzeoloģes Ninas Saimonas (Nina Simon) teorētiskā ietvara "līdzdalības iesaistīšanās", projekta mērķis ir izpētīt līdzdalības iesaistīšanās dinamikas noteicošos faktoros, modeļus un sekas muzeju nozarē, veicot izpēti caur muzejizglītības prizmu – vienu no trīs muzeja pamata funkcijām. Pētījumā tiks apzināti līdzdalības attīstības determinanti muzeju nozarē, kā arī, piemērojot līdzdalīgas pētniecības (participatory action research) metodoloģiju, no prakses kopienu (community of practice) perspektīvas, (1) kartējot muzeju izglītības programmas akreditētajos muzejos Latvijā un nosakot noteicošos faktoros, kas veido vai ierobežo muzeju centienus īstenot arvien intensīvākus līdzdalības iesaistes modeļus, (2) pētot dominējošos modeļus un attieksmi pret līdzdalīgu iesaisti no dažādu Latvijas prakses kopienu perspektīvas, kā arī (3) analizējot līdzdalīgas iesaistes nospiedumu plašākā sociālpolitiskajā kontekstā - gan attiecībā uz iesaistīto kopienu dzīvi, gan uz muzeju darbību, gan starpnozaru sadarbību, kultūras mantojuma politiku un starptautisko atzinību.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

MEET

Researchers

Baiba Tjarve (orcid:0000-0003-0770-3377), Gints Klāsons
(orcid:0000-0002-2979-5463)

Organizations

Latvian Academy of Culture

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [FLPP MEET DPP](#)

Description:

Projekts atbilst aktuālajam muzeoloģijas fokusam, kas uzsver sociālo iesaisti kā būtisku muzeju uzdevumu un ko apliecina Starptautiskās Muzeju padomes iniciatīva mainīt jēdziena "muzejs" definīciju, iekļaujot tajā muzeju pienākumu strādāt ar kopienu līdzdalību. Iedvesmojoties no muzeoloģes Ninas Saimonas (Nina Simon) teorētiskā ietvara "līdzdalības iesaistīšanās", projekta mērķis ir izpētīt līdzdalības iesaistīšanās dinamikas noteicošos faktorus, modeļus un sekas muzeju nozarē, veicot izpēti caur muzejizglītības prizmu – vienu no trīs muzeja pamata funkcijām. Pētījumā tiks apzināti līdzdalības attīstības determinanti muzeju nozarē, kā arī, piemērojot līdzdalīgas pētniecības (participatory action research) metodoloģiju, no prakses kopienu (community of practice) perspektīvas, (1) kartējot muzeju izglītības programmas akreditētajos muzejos Latvijā un nosakot noteicošos faktorus, kas veido vai ierobežo muzeju centienus īstenot arvien intensīvākus līdzdalības iesaistes modeļus, (2) pētot dominējošos modeļus un attieksmi pret līdzdalīgu iesaisti no dažādu Latvijas prakses kopienu perspektīvas, kā arī (3) analizējot līdzdalīgas iesaistes nospiedumu plašākā sociālpolitiskajā kontekstā - gan attiecībā uz iesaistīto kopienu dzīvi, gan uz muzeju darbību, gan starpnozaru sadarbību, kultūras mantojuma politiku un starptautisko atzinību.

Researchers:

[Baiba Tjarve \(orcid:0000-0003-0770-3377\)](#)

[Gints Klāsons \(orcid:0000-0002-2979-5463\)](#)

Organizations:

[Latvian Academy of Culture](#)

Contact: [Tjarve Baiba \(baiba.tjarve@lka.edu.lv\)](mailto:baiba.tjarve@lka.edu.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Latvian Council of Science](#)

Grants: [MEET](#)

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date: 2025-02-05

4. Templates

Descriptions

Akreditēto muzeju vadītāju aptaujas dati

Kvantitatīvas socioloģiskas aptaujas dati, iegūti ar pašreizpildes metodi interneta vidē programmētas anketas veidā.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Kvantitatīvas socioloģiskas aptaujas dati, iegūti ar pašreizpildes metodi interneta vidē programmētas anketas veidā.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Survey data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

CSV

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Sociālo un humanitāro zinātņu pētniekiem, kas pielieto līdzdalības pētījuma dizainu, pēta muzejus un sociālās iesaistes faktorus tajos

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Dublin Core

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo repozitoriju pārvalda CERN, nodrošinot mūža pieeju un ilgstamību, kā arī datu drošību

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

SPSS, Excel

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Programmas, kas darbojas ar .csv formātu

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

Valsts finansēto pētniecības programmu datiem un to metadatiem pēc noklusējuma jābūt pieejamiem universālajā Creative Commons licencē

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Baiba Tjarve (orcid: [0000-0003-0770-3377](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0770-3377))

Pētījuma projekta vadītājs sadarbībā ar institūcijas datu pārvaldības speciālistu

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

Dati glabājas mapē Latvijas Kultūras akadēmijas mākoņserverī, kas pieejama tikai atbildīgajiem pētniekiem

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Akreditēto muzeju muzejpedagogu raksturojuma dati

Kvantitatīvas socioloģiskas aptaujas dati, iegūti ar pašreizpildes metodi interneta vidē programmētas anketas veidā.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Kvantitatīvas socioloģiskas aptaujas dati, iegūti ar pašreizpildes metodi interneta vidē programmētas anketas veidā.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Survey data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

CSV

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Sociālo un humanitāro zinātņu pētniekiem, kas pielieto līdzdalības pētījuma dizainu, pēta muzejus un sociālās iesaistes faktoros tajos

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Dublin Core

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo repozitoriju pārvalda CERN, nodrošinot mūža pieeju un ilgstamību, kā arī datu drošību

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

SPSS, Excel

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Programmas, kas darbojas ar .csv formātu

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

Valsts finansēto pētniecības programmu datiem un to metadatiem pēc noklusējuma jābūt pieejamiem universālajā Creative Commons licencē

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Baiba Tjarve (orcid: [0000-0003-0770-3377](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0770-3377))

Pētījuma projekta vadītājs sadarbībā ar institūcijas datu pārvaldības speciālistu

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

Dati glabājas mapē Latvijas Kultūras akadēmijas mākoņserverī, kas pieejama tikai atbildīgajiem pētniekiem

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Raiņa un Aspazijas vasarnīcas gadījums: intervija ar skolotāju

Pētnieku intervija Rīgas Strazdumuižas jauniešu skolotāju par pieredzi iesaistoties Raiņa un Aspazijas vasarnīcas projekta "Sajūtu ceļojums" tapšanā.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Pētnieku intervija Rīgas Strazdumuižas jauniešu skolotāju par pieredzi iesaistoties Raiņa un Aspazijas vasarnīcas projekta "Sajūtu ceļojums" tapšanā.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

Others

.doc

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Sociālo un humanitāro zinātņu pētniekiem, kas pielieto līdzdalības pētījuma dizainu, pēta muzejus un sociālās iesaistes faktorus tajos

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Dublin Core

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, no access (access is denied, files will be opened only through contact person to the authors)

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo repozitoriju pārvalda CERN, nodrošinot mūža pieeju un ilgstamību, kā arī datu drošību

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Jebkura teksta lasīšanas programmatūra

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Jebkura teksta lasīšanas programmatūra, kas spēj atvērt .doc failus

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

Valsts finansēto pētniecības programmu datiem un to metadatiem pēc noklusējuma jābūt pieejamiem universālajā Creative Commons licencē

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

No

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Baiba Tjarve (orcid: [0000-0003-0770-3377](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0770-3377))

Pētījuma projekta vadītājs sadarbībā ar institūcijas datu pārvaldības speciālistu

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

Dati glabājas mapē Latvijas Kultūras akadēmijas mākoņserverī, kas pieejama tikai atbildīgajiem pētniekiem

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Pseudonymization

Mutisks brīdinājums par nosacījumiem, datu anonimizēšanu. Visi informanti deva piekrišanu.

Raiņa un Aspazijas vasarnīcas gadījums: intervijas ar jauniešiem

Pētnieku intervijas ar Rīgas Strazdumuižas jauniešiem par pieredzi iesaistoties Raiņa un Aspazijas vasarnīcas projekta "Sajūtu ceļojums" tapšanā, testēšanā. Pieredzes dimensiju raksturojums.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Pētnieku intervijas ar Rīgas Strazdumuižas jauniešiem par pieredzi iesaistoties Raiņa un Aspazijas vasarnīcas projekta "Sajūtu ceļojums" tapšanā, testēšanā. Pieredzes dimensiju raksturojums.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

Others

.doc

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Sociālo un humanitāro zinātņu pētniekiem, kas pielieto līdzdalības pētījuma dizainu, pēta muzejus un sociālās iesaistes faktorus tajos

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Dublin Core

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, no access (access is denied, files will be opened only through contact person to the authors)

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo repozitoriju pārvalda CERN, nodrošinot mūža pieeju un ilgstamību, kā arī datu drošību

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Jebkura teksta lasīšanas programmatūra

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Jebkura teksta lasīšanas programmatūra, kas spēj atvērt .doc failus

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

Valsts finansēto pētniecības programmu datiem un to metadatiem pēc noklusējuma jābūt pieejamiem universālajā Creative Commons licencē

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

No

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Baiba Tjarve (orcid: [0000-0003-0770-3377](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0770-3377))

Pētījuma projekta vadītājs sadarbībā ar institūcijas datu pārvaldības speciālistu

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

Dati glabājas mapē Latvijas Kultūras akadēmijas mākoņserverī, kas pieejama tikai atbildīgajiem pētniekiem

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Pseudonymization

Izmantota piekrišanas forma par dalību pētījumā. Jauniešiem, kas jaunāki par 16 gadiem - vecāku atļauja. Visi informanti deva piekrišanu.

Raiņa un Aspazijas vasarnīcas gadījums: intervijas ar muzeja pārstāvjiem

Intervijas ar muzeja pārstāvjiem par Raiņa un Aspazijas vasarnīcas projekta "Sajūtu ceļojums" veidošanas pieredzi, nozīmi, jauniešu iesaisti projekta tapšanās laikā.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Intervijas ar muzeja pārstāvjiem par Raiņa un Aspazijas vasarnīcas projekta "Sajūtu ceļojums" veidošanas pieredzi, nozīmi, jauniešu iesaisti projekta tapšanās laikā.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

Others

.doc

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Sociālo un humanitāro zinātņu pētniekiem, kas pielieto līdzdalības pētījuma dizainu, pēta muzejus un sociālās iesaistes faktorus tajos

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Dublin Core

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, no access (access is denied, files will be opened only through contact person to the authors)

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo repozitoriju pārvalda CERN, nodrošinot mūža pieeju un ilgstamību, kā arī datu drošību

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Jebkura teksta lasīšanas programmatūra

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Jebkura teksta lasīšanas programmatūra, kas spēj atvērt .doc failus

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

Valsts finansēto pētniecības programmu datiem un to metadatiem pēc noklusējuma jābūt pieejamiem universālajā Creative Commons licencē

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

No

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Baiba Tjarve (orcid: [0000-0003-0770-3377](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0770-3377))

Pētījuma projekta vadītājs sadarbībā ar institūcijas datu pārvaldības speciālistu

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

Dati glabājas mapē Latvijas Kultūras akadēmijas mākoņserverī, kas pieejama tikai atbildīgajiem pētniekiem

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Pseudonymization

Mutisks brīdinājums par nosacījumiem, datu anonimizēšanu. Visi informanti deva piekrišanu.

Raiņa un Aspazijas vasarnīcas gadījums: fokusgrupa (apvērstā prāta vētra)

Kopīga saruna, apvērstā prāta vētra, ar jauniešiem un skolotāju, atbildot uz jautājumiem par muzeju pieredzi kopumā, idejām, kādam nav un ir jābūt muzejam.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Kopīga saruna, apvērstā prāta vētra, ar jauniešiem un skolotāju, atbildot uz jautājumiem par muzeju pieredzi kopumā, idejām, kādam nav un ir jābūt muzejam.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

Others

.doc

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Sociālo un humanitāro zinātņu pētniekiem, kas pielieto līdzdalības pētījuma dizainu, pēta muzejus un sociālās iesaistes faktorus tajos

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Dublin Core

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, no access (access is denied, files will be opened only through contact person to the authors)

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo repozitoriju pārvalda CERN, nodrošinot mūža pieeju un ilgstamību, kā arī datu drošību

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Jebkura teksta lasīšanas programmatūra

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Jebkura teksta lasīšanas programmatūra, kas spēj atvērt .doc failus

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

Valsts finansēto pētniecības programmu datiem un to metadatiem pēc noklusējuma jābūt pieejamiem universālajā Creative Commons licencē

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

No

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Baiba Tjarve (orcid: [0000-0003-0770-3377](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0770-3377))

Pētījuma projekta vadītājs sadarbībā ar institūcijas datu pārvaldības speciālistu

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

Dati glabājas mapē Latvijas Kultūras akadēmijas mākoņserverī, kas pieejama tikai atbildīgajiem pētniekiem

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Pseudonymization

Izmantota piekrišanas forma par dalību pētījumā. Jauniešiem, kas jaunāki par 16 gadiem - vecāku atļauja. Visi informanti deva piekrišanu.

Raiņa un Aspazijas vasarnīcas gadījums: peer-to-peer intervija

Peer-to-peer intervija, kur Rīgas Strazdumuižas jauniešieš reflektē par pieredzi iesaistoties Raiņa un Aspazijas vasarnīcas projekta "Sajūtu ceļojums" tapšanā. Pieredzes dimensiju iztirzāšana.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Peer-to-peer intervija, kur Rīgas Strazdumuižas jauniešieš reflektē par pieredzi iesaistoties Raiņa un Aspazijas vasarnīcas projekta "Sajūtu ceļojums" tapšanā. Pieredzes dimensiju iztirzāšana.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

Others

.doc

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Sociālo un humanitāro zinātņu pētniekiem, kas pielieto līdzdalības pētījuma dizainu, pēta muzejus un sociālās iesaistes faktorus tajos

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Dublin Core

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, no access (access is denied, files will be opened only through contact person to the authors)

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo repozitoriju pārvalda CERN, nodrošinot mūža pieeju un ilgstamību, kā arī datu drošību

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Jebkura teksta lasīšanas programmatūra

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Jebkura teksta lasīšanas programmatūra, kas spēj atvērt .doc failus

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

Valsts finansēto pētniecības programmu datiem un to metadatiem pēc noklusējuma jābūt pieejamiem universālajā Creative Commons licencē

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

No

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Baiba Tjarve (orcid: [0000-0003-0770-3377](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0770-3377))

Pētījuma projekta vadītājs sadarbībā ar institūcijas datu pārvaldības speciālistu

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

Dati glabājas mapē Latvijas Kultūras akadēmijas mākoņserverī, kas pieejama tikai atbildīgajiem pētniekiem

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Pseudonymization

Izmantota piekrišanas forma par dalību pētījumā. Jauniešiem, kas jaunāki par 16 gadiem - vecāku atļauja. Visi informanti deva piekrišanu.

Kalāču gadījums: intervijas ar muzeja pārstāvjiem

Intervijas ar Eduarda Veidenbauma muzeja "Kalāči" pārstāvjiem par jauniešu iesaisti muzeja darbībā.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Intervijas ar Eduarda Veidenbauma muzeja "Kalāči" pārstāvjiem par jauniešu iesaisti muzeja darbībā.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

Others

.doc

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Sociālo un humanitāro zinātņu pētniekiem, kas pielieto līdzdalības pētījuma dizainu, pēta muzejus un sociālās iesaistes faktorus tajos

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Dublin Core

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, no access (access is denied, files will be opened only through contact person to the authors)

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo repozitoriju pārvalda CERN, nodrošinot mūža pieeju un ilgstamību, kā arī datu drošību

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Jebkura teksta lasīšanas programmatūra

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Jebkura teksta lasīšanas programmatūra, kas spēj atvērt .doc failus

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

Valsts finansēto pētniecības programmu datiem un to metadatiem pēc noklusējuma jābūt pieejamiem universālajā Creative Commons licencē

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

No

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Baiba Tjarve (orcid: [0000-0003-0770-3377](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0770-3377))

Pētījuma projekta vadītājs sadarbībā ar institūcijas datu pārvaldības speciālistu

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

Dati glabājas mapē Latvijas Kultūras akadēmijas mākoņserverī, kas pieejama tikai atbildīgajiem pētniekiem

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Pseudonymization

Mutisks brīdinājums par nosacījumiem, datu anonimizēšanu. Visi informanti deva piekrišanu.

Kalāču gadījums: intervijas ar jauniešiem

Intervijas ar Eduarda Veidenbauma muzeja "Kalāči" darbībā iesaistītajiem jauniešiem par viņu pieredzi. Jauniešu refleksijas par ceļa kartēm, kur 1-2 jaunieši vienas intervijas laikā viens otram un pētniekam pastāsta par uzzīmēto

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Intervijas ar Eduarda Veidenbauma muzeja "Kalāči" darbībā iesaistītajiem jauniešiem par viņu pieredzi. Jauniešu refleksijas par ceļa kartēm, kur 1-2 jaunieši vienas intervijas laikā viens otram un pētniekam pastāsta par uzzīmēto

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

Others

.doc

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Sociālo un humanitāro zinātņu pētniekiem, kas pielieto līdzdalības pētījuma dizainu, pēta muzejus un sociālās iesaistes faktorus tajos

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Dublin Core

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, no access (access is denied, files will be opened only through contact person to the authors)

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo repozitoriju pārvalda CERN, nodrošinot mūža pieeju un ilgstamību, kā arī datu drošību

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Jebkura teksta lasīšanas programmatūra

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Jebkura teksta lasīšanas programmatūra, kas spēj atvērt .doc failus

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

Valsts finansēto pētniecības programmu datiem un to metadatiem pēc noklusējuma jābūt pieejamiem universālajā Creative Commons licencē

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

No

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Baiba Tjarve (orcid: [0000-0003-0770-3377](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0770-3377))

Pētījuma projekta vadītājs sadarbībā ar institūcijas datu pārvaldības speciālistu

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

Dati glabājas mapē Latvijas Kultūras akadēmijas mākoņserverī, kas pieejama tikai atbildīgajiem pētniekiem

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Pseudonymization

Izmantota piekrišanas forma par dalību pētījumā. Jauniešiem, kas jaunāki par 16 gadiem - vecāku atļauja. Visi informanti deva piekrišanu.

Kalāču gadījums: jauniešu veidotās ceļa kartes

Eduarda Veidenbauma muzeja "Kalāči" darbībā iesaistīto jauniešu pieredzes vizualizācijas - ceļa kartes.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Eduarda Veidenbauma muzeja "Kalāči" darbībā iesaistīto jauniešu pieredzes vizualizācijas - ceļa kartes.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Other

skenēta vizualizācija

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

PDF

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Sociālo un humanitāro zinātņu pētniekiem, kas pielieto līdzdalības pētījuma dizainu, pēta muzejus un sociālās iesaistes faktorus tajos

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Dublin Core

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, no access (access is denied, files will be opened only through contact person to the authors)

Dati iegūti no jauniešiem, sensitīvi dati

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo repozitoriju pārvalda CERN, nodrošinot mūža pieeju un ilgstamību, kā arī datu drošību

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Jebkura teksta lasīšanas programmatūra

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Jebkura programmatūra, kas spēj atvērt PDF failus

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

Valsts finansēto pētniecības programmu datiem un to metadatiem pēc noklusējuma jābūt pieejamiem universālajā Creative Commons licencē

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

No

Dati iegūti no jauniešiem, satur sensitīvu informāciju

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Baiba Tjarve (orcid: [0000-0003-0770-3377](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0770-3377))

Pētījuma projekta vadītājs sadarbībā ar institūcijas datu pārvaldības speciālistu

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

Dati glabājas mapē Latvijas Kultūras akadēmijas mākoņserverī, kas pieejama tikai atbildīgajiem pētniekiem

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

Dati iegūti no jauniešiem

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Pseudonymization

Izmantota piekrišanas forma par dalību pētījumā. Jauniešiem, kas jaunāki par 16 gadiem - vecāku atļauja. Visi informanti deva piekrišanu.

Kalāču gadījums: muzeja pārstāvja ceļa karte

Eduarda Veidenbauma muzeja "Kalāči" muzejpedagoģes pieredzes vizualizācijas - ceļa kartes.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Intervijas ar muzeja pārstāvjiem par Raiņa un Aspazijas vasarnīcas projekta "Sajūtu ceļojums" veidošanas pieredzi, nozīmi, jauniešu iesaisti projekta tapšanās laikā.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Other

skenēta vizualizācija

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

PDF

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Sociālo un humanitāro zinātņu pētniekiem, kas pielieto līdzdalības pētījuma dizainu, pēta muzejus un sociālās iesaistes faktorus tajos

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Dublin Core

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, no access (access is denied, files will be opened only through contact person to the authors)

Dati iegūti no jauniešiem, sensitīvi dati

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo repozitoriju pārvalda CERN, nodrošinot mūža pieeju un ilgstamību, kā arī datu drošību

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Jebkura teksta lasīšanas programmatūra

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Jebkura programmatūra, kas spēj atvērt PDF failus

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

Valsts finansēto pētniecības programmu datiem un to metadatiem pēc noklusējuma jābūt pieejamiem universālajā Creative Commons licencē

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

No

Dati iegūti no jauniešiem, satur sensitīvu informāciju

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Baiba Tjarve (orcid: [0000-0003-0770-3377](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0770-3377))

Pētījuma projekta vadītājs sadarbībā ar institūcijas datu pārvaldības speciālistu

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

Dati glabājas mapē Latvijas Kultūras akadēmijas mākoņserverī, kas pieejama tikai atbildīgajiem pētniekiem

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

Dati iegūti no jauniešiem

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Pseudonymization

Mutisks brīdinājums par nosacījumiem, datu anonimizēšanu. Informants deva piekrišanu.

Olaines Vēstures un mākslas muzeja gadījums: intervija ar muzeja pārstāvjiem

Intervija ar Olaines Vēstures un mākslas muzeja pārstāvi par jauniešu iesaisti muzeja darbībā.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Intervija ar Olaines Vēstures un mākslas muzeja pārstāvi par jauniešu iesaisti muzeja darbībā.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

Others

.doc

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Sociālo un humanitāro zinātņu pētniekiem, kas pielieto līdzdalības pētījuma dizainu, pēta muzejus un sociālās iesaistes faktorus tajos

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Dublin Core

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, no access (access is denied, files will be opened only through contact person to the authors)

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo repozitoriju pārvalda CERN, nodrošinot mūža pieeju un ilgstamību, kā arī datu drošību

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Jebkura teksta lasīšanas programmatūra

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Jebkura teksta lasīšanas programmatūra, kas spēj atvērt .doc failus

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

Valsts finansēto pētniecības programmu datiem un to metadatiem pēc noklusējuma jābūt pieejamiem universālajā Creative Commons licencē

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

No

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Baiba Tjarve (orcid: [0000-0003-0770-3377](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0770-3377))

Pētījuma projekta vadītājs sadarbībā ar institūcijas datu pārvaldības speciālistu

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

Dati glabājas mapē Latvijas Kultūras akadēmijas mākoņserverī, kas pieejama tikai atbildīgajiem pētniekiem

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Pseudonymization

Mutisks brīdinājums par nosacījumiem, datu anonimizēšanu. Visi informanti deva piekrišanu.

Olaines Vēstures un mākslas muzeja gadījums: intervijas ar jauniešiem

Intervija ar Olaines Vēstures un mākslas muzeja muzeja darbībā iesaistītajiem jauniešiem.
Katrā intervijā 1 līdz 2 jaunieši kopā ar pētnieku.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Intervija ar Olaines Vēstures un mākslas muzeja muzeja darbībā iesaistītajiem jauniešiem. Katrā intervijā 1 līdz 2 jaunieši kopā ar pētnieku.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

Others

.doc

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Sociālo un humanitāro zinātņu pētniekiem, kas pielieto līdzdalības pētījuma dizainu, pēta muzejus un sociālās iesaistes faktorus tajos

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Dublin Core

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, no access (access is denied, files will be opened only through contact person to the authors)

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo repozitoriju pārvalda CERN, nodrošinot mūža pieeju un ilgstamību, kā arī datu drošību

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Jebkura teksta lasīšanas programmatūra

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Jebkura teksta lasīšanas programmatūra, kas spēj atvērt .doc failus

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

Valsts finansēto pētniecības programmu datiem un to metadatiem pēc noklusējuma jābūt pieejamiem universālajā Creative Commons licencē

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

No

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Baiba Tjarve (orcid: [0000-0003-0770-3377](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0770-3377))

Pētījuma projekta vadītājs sadarbībā ar institūcijas datu pārvaldības speciālistu

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

Dati glabājas mapē Latvijas Kultūras akadēmijas mākoņserverī, kas pieejama tikai atbildīgajiem pētniekiem

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Pseudonymization

Izmantota piekrišanas forma par dalību pētījumā. Jauniešiem, kas jaunāki par 16 gadiem - vecāku atļauja. Visi informanti deva piekrišanu.

Olaines Vēstures un mākslas muzeja gadījums: fokusgrupa ar jauniešiem

Fokusgrupa ar Olaines Vēstures un mākslas muzeja darbībā iesaistītajiem jauniešiem par motivāciju piedalīties arheoloģiskajos izrakumos.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Fokusgrupa ar Olaines Vēstures un mākslas muzeja darbībā iesaistītajiem jauniešiem par motivāciju piedalīties arheoloģiskajos izrakumos.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

Others

.doc

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Sociālo un humanitāro zinātņu pētniekiem, kas pielieto līdzdalības pētījuma dizainu, pēta muzejus un sociālās iesaistes faktorus tajos

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Dublin Core

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, no access (access is denied, files will be opened only through contact person to the authors)

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo repozitoriju pārvalda CERN, nodrošinot mūža pieeju un ilgstamību, kā arī datu drošību

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Jebkura teksta lasīšanas programmatūra

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Jebkura teksta lasīšanas programmatūra, kas spēj atvērt .doc failus

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

Valsts finansēto pētniecības programmu datiem un to metadatiem pēc noklusējuma jābūt pieejamiem universālajā Creative Commons licencē

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

No

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Baiba Tjarve (orcid: [0000-0003-0770-3377](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0770-3377))

Pētījuma projekta vadītājs sadarbībā ar institūcijas datu pārvaldības speciālistu

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

Dati glabājas mapē Latvijas Kultūras akadēmijas mākoņserverī, kas pieejama tikai atbildīgajiem pētniekiem

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Pseudonymization

Izmantota piekrišanas forma par dalību pētījumā. Jauniešiem, kas jaunāki par 16 gadiem - vecāku atļauja. Visi informanti deva piekrišanu.

LNMM gadījums: intervijas ar muzeja pārstāvjiem

Intervijas ar Latvijas Nacionālais mākslas muzeja pārstāvjiem par jauniešu iesaisti muzeja darbībā, jauniešu klubu.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Intervijas ar Latvijas Nacionālais mākslas muzeja pārstāvjiem par jauniešu iesaisti muzeja darbībā, jauniešu klubu.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

Others

.doc

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Sociālo un humanitāro zinātņu pētniekiem, kas pielieto līdzdalības pētījuma dizainu, pēta muzejus un sociālās iesaistes faktorus tajos

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Dublin Core

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, no access (access is denied, files will be opened only through contact person to the authors)

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo repozitoriju pārvalda CERN, nodrošinot mūža pieeju un ilgstamību, kā arī datu drošību

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Jebkura teksta lasīšanas programmatūra

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Jebkura teksta lasīšanas programmatūra, kas spēj atvērt .doc failus

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

Valsts finansēto pētniecības programmu datiem un to metadatiem pēc noklusējuma jābūt pieejamiem universālajā Creative Commons licencē

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

No

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Baiba Tjarve (orcid: [0000-0003-0770-3377](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0770-3377))

Pētījuma projekta vadītājs sadarbībā ar institūcijas datu pārvaldības speciālistu

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

Dati glabājas mapē Latvijas Kultūras akadēmijas mākoņserverī, kas pieejama tikai atbildīgajiem pētniekiem

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Pseudonymization

Mutisks brīdinājums par nosacījumiem, datu anonimizēšanu. Visi informanti deva piekrišanu.

LNMM gadījums: intervijas ar jauniešiem

Intervijas ar Latvijas Nacionālais mākslas muzeja iesaistītajiem jauniešiem par pieredzi muzeja darbībā, jauniešu klubu.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Intervijas ar Latvijas Nacionālais mākslas muzeja iesaistītajiem jauniešiem par pieredzi muzeja darbībā, jauniešu klubu.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

Others

.doc

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Sociālo un humanitāro zinātņu pētniekiem, kas pielieto līdzdalības pētījuma dizainu, pēta muzejus un sociālās iesaistes faktorus tajos

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Dublin Core

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, no access (access is denied, files will be opened only through contact person to the authors)

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo repozitoriju pārvalda CERN, nodrošinot mūža pieeju un ilgstamību, kā arī datu drošību

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Jebkura teksta lasīšanas programmatūra

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Jebkura teksta lasīšanas programmatūra, kas spēj atvērt .doc failus

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

Valsts finansēto pētniecības programmu datiem un to metadatiem pēc noklusējuma jābūt pieejamiem universālajā Creative Commons licencē

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

No

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Baiba Tjarve (orcid: [0000-0003-0770-3377](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0770-3377))

Pētījuma projekta vadītājs sadarbībā ar institūcijas datu pārvaldības speciālistu

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

Dati glabājas mapē Latvijas Kultūras akadēmijas mākoņserverī, kas pieejama tikai atbildīgajiem pētniekiem

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Pseudonymization

Izmantota piekrišanas forma par dalību pētījumā un datu izmantošanu.

LNMM gadījums: jauniešu iesūtītie foto

Jauniešu iesūtītās fotogrāfijas, kas attēlo Latvijas Nacionālais mākslas muzeja darbības, jauniešu kluba pieredzēto.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Jauniešu iesūtītās fotogrāfijas, kas attēlo Latvijas Nacionālais mākslas muzeja darbības, jauniešu kluba pieredzēto.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Other

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

Others

.jpg

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Sociālo un humanitāro zinātņu pētniekiem, kas pielieto līdzdalības pētījuma dizainu, pēta muzejus un sociālās iesaistes faktorus tajos

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Dublin Core

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, no access (access is denied, files will be opened only through contact person to the authors)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo repozitoriju pārvalda CERN, nodrošinot mūža pieeju un ilgstamību, kā arī datu drošību

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Jebkura attēlu lasīšanas programmatūra

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Jebkura attēlu lasīšanas programmatūra, kas spēj atvērt .jpg failus

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

Valsts finansēto pētniecības programmu datiem un to metadatiem pēc noklusējuma jābūt pieejamiem universālajā Creative Commons licencē

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

No

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Baiba Tjarve (orcid: [0000-0003-0770-3377](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0770-3377))

Pētījuma projekta vadītājs sadarbībā ar institūcijas datu pārvaldības speciālistu

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

Dati glabājas mapē Latvijas Kultūras akadēmijas mākoņserverī, kas pieejama tikai atbildīgajiem pētniekiem

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

Dati iegūti no jauniešiem

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Pseudonymization

Izmantota piekrišanas forma par dalību pētījumā un datu izmantošanu.

Rotko muzeja gadījums: intervijas ar jauniešiem

Dubultintervijas ar Rotko muzeja iesaistītajiem jauniešiem par pieredzi muzeja darbībā, jauniešu klubu.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Dubultintervijas ar Rotko muzeja iesaistītajiem jauniešiem par pieredzi muzeja darbībā, jauniešu klubu.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

Others

.doc

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Sociālo un humanitāro zinātņu pētniekiem, kas pielieto līdzdalības pētījuma dizainu, pēta muzejus un sociālās iesaistes faktorus tajos

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Dublin Core

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, no access (access is denied, files will be opened only through contact person to the authors)

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo repozitoriju pārvalda CERN, nodrošinot mūža pieeju un ilgstamību, kā arī datu drošību

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Jebkura teksta lasīšanas programmatūra

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Jebkura teksta lasīšanas programmatūra, kas spēj atvērt .doc failus

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

Valsts finansēto pētniecības programmu datiem un to metadatiem pēc noklusējuma jābūt pieejamiem universālajā Creative Commons licencē

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

No

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Baiba Tjarve (orcid: [0000-0003-0770-3377](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0770-3377))

Pētījuma projekta vadītājs sadarbībā ar institūcijas datu pārvaldības speciālistu

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

Dati glabājas mapē Latvijas Kultūras akadēmijas mākoņserverī, kas pieejama tikai atbildīgajiem pētniekiem

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Pseudonymization

Izmantota piekrišanas forma par dalību pētījumā. Jauniešiem, kas jaunāki par 16 gadiem - vecāku atļauja. Visi informanti deva piekrišanu.

Ekspertu intervijas

Sarunas ar ekspertiem par projektā svarīgām tēmām, noskaidrojot informāciju par gadījumiem, kur tiek iesaistīti jaunieši, kā arī precizētu muzejpedagogu darbu anketas jautājumus

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Sarunas ar ekspertiem par projektā svarīgām tēmām, noskaidrojot informāciju par gadījumiem, kur tiek iesaistīti jaunieši, kā arī precizētu muzejpedagogu darbu anketas jautājumus

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

Others

.doc

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Sociālo un humanitāro zinātņu pētniekiem, kas pielieto līdzdalības pētījuma dizainu, pēta muzejus un sociālās iesaistes faktorus tajos

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Dublin Core

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, no access (access is denied, files will be opened only through contact person to the authors)

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo repozitoriju pārvalda CERN, nodrošinot mūža pieeju un ilgstamību, kā arī datu drošību

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Jebkura teksta lasīšanas programmatūra

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Jebkura teksta lasīšanas programmatūra, kas spēj atvērt .doc failus

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

Valsts finansēto pētniecības programmu datiem un to metadatiem pēc noklusējuma jābūt pieejamiem universālajā Creative Commons licencē

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

No

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Baiba Tjarve (orcid: [0000-0003-0770-3377](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0770-3377))

Pētījuma projekta vadītājs sadarbībā ar institūcijas datu pārvaldības speciālistu

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

Dati glabājas mapē Latvijas Kultūras akadēmijas mākoņserverī, kas pieejama tikai atbildīgajiem pētniekiem

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

Transkripti nav anonimizēti. Anonimizācija tiek nodrošināta reprezentējot datus zinātniskos rakstos, prezentācijās.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Pseudonymization

Mutisks brīdinājums par nosacījumiem, datu anonimizēšanu. Informanti deva piekrišanu.

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